

Nitromethane as a Polar Solvent. Part I. Nature of the Solutions of Acids and Bases in Nitromethane

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Nitromethane forms solvates with antimony(v) chloride, aluminium(III) chloride, aluminium(III) bromide, titanium(IV) chloride, titanium(IV) bromide, titanium(IV) fluoride, calcium chloride, manganese chloride, cadmium chloride, copper(II) chloride, zinc chloride, mercuric chloride, and nickel chloride. These solvates have been isolated. Conductometric studies indicate formation of compounds with tin(IV) chloride, arsenic(III) chloride, and antimony(III) chloride. Conductometric studies also indicate formation of complexes with the protonic acids, viz., fluorosulphuric, sulphuric, formic, and acetic acid. On the basis of the conductance of the solutions, the Lewis acids can be arranged in order of their decreasing strength as: $\text{SbCl}_5 > \text{SnCl}_4 > \text{TiCl}_4 > \text{AsCl}_3$ and protonic acids as: $\text{HSO}_3\text{F} > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{HCOOH} > \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$.

Conductometric studies of bases, viz., pyridine, α -picoline, dimethylaniline, and quinoline, indicate the order of basicity as quinoline $>$ α -picoline $>$ pyridine $>$ dimethylaniline. The value of slopes of plots of $\log c$ vs $\log \alpha c$ in these cases is $\frac{1}{2}$, indicating their ionisation as uniunivalent electrolytes. Conductometric studies of the bases, viz., piperidine, *n*-butylamine, triethylamine, and benzylamine, show that these are stronger bases than the first set and their order of basicity as: piperidine $>$ triethylamine $>$ *n*-butylamine $>$ benzylamine. The value of slopes in these cases is $-3/4$, indicating that probably these dimerise. On the basis of this work, the autoionisation of nitromethane may be represented as:

Nitromethane has been used as a solvent and a reaction medium for quite some time and a large amount of disconnected work has already been reported. Conductances of a large number of compounds including a few Lewis acids¹⁻³, protonic acids⁶, and organic tertiary bases⁷ have been measured and the formation of solvates with different compounds has been studied⁸⁻¹⁰. Nitromethane has also been studied as a medium for acid-base titra-

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- Gorcubein and Danilova, *Trody Kievvet Inst.*, 1957, **13**, 301.
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tions, using potentiometric method¹¹ or visual indicators¹² to detect the end point. No systematic work to ascertain its nature as a solvent has, however, been carried out. Some of the physical constants of nitromethane are listed below.

TABLE I

		Ref. No.
Melting point	-28.55°	13
Boiling point	101.2° at 760 mm	13
Density	1.13816 at 20°	13
Dielectric constant	38.57 at 20°	14,15
Surface tension	36.97 dyne/cm at 20°	16
Viscosity	0.632 centipoise at 25°	17
Dipole moment	3.5 D in benzene	18
Trouton's constant	22.1	19
Sp. conductance	1×10^{-8} ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ at 25°	20
Heat of vaporisation at 99.9°	134.94 cal./g.	21,22
Heat of fusion at m.p.	2319 ± 3.0 cal. mole	19

Nitromethane has thus a convenient working range and a fairly high dielectric constant (cf. water²³, 81.8 at 18°; dimethylformamide²⁴, 36.79 at 25°). Its conductance is comparable to that of water²⁵ which indicates the possibility of its autoionisation. A high dipole moment (3.5 D) indicates its highly polar nature, leading to its association. It is therefore expected to be a fairly good solvent both for organic and inorganic compounds.

Pure nitromethane is known to undergo enolisation²⁶⁻²⁸; there is an equilibrium between the pseudo-acid and the *aci* forms, which represent the two extremes. The actual situation may be nearer to form (Z).

11. Streulter, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 1652.
12. Fritz and Fulda, *ibid.*, 1953, **25**, 1837.
13. Toops, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 304.
14. Timmermans *et al.*, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1955, **65**, 5; **64**, 600.
15. Wiswall and Smith, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1941, **9**, 356.
16. Roland and Lek, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1931, **40**, 177.
17. Holcomb and Dirsey, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1949, **41**, 2788.
18. Cramm and Hamond, "Organic Chemistry", p. 152.
19. Jones and Giaque, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 883.
20. Elias and Schiff, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 595.
21. Mathews, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 562.
22. Karapet, *Yanti. Zhur. Fiz-khim.*, 1926, **32**, 554.
23. International Critical Table, 1929, VI, 77-78.
24. Dawson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 373.
25. International Critical Table, 1929, VI, pp. 142, 152.
26. Hantzsch and Schultze, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 699, 2251.
27. Hedley, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1195.
28. Hantzsch, *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 1001.

The enolic hydrogen in form (E) is acidic in nature and can be easily replaced by Na^+ ions in alkaline medium, affording sodium nitromethane. IR²⁹⁻³¹ and Raman spectra³² of sodium nitromethane have been studied to throw light on its structure as well as on that of nitromethane. Thus there is a possibility of hydrogen-bond formation, resulting in association of nitromethane which may be represented as:

Association can also be the result of dipole interaction as :

That nitromethane is an associated liquid is evident from a comparison of its boiling point with that of nitrotrifluoromethane (b.p. -31.1°) in which there is no possibility of hydrogen-bond formation. This view is further supported by a comparison of the Trouton constant values of these two compounds (CH_3NO_2 , 22.1; CF_3NO_2 , 21.3).

29. Jonathan, *J. Mol. Spectroscopy*, 1961, **7**, 105.

30. Fever *et al.*, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 431.

31. Yarwood *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5991.

32. Smith and Neilsen, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 706.

The following equilibria may therefore be proposed as existing in the pure liquid and may indicate that nitromethane acts as a protonic solvent.

or

But since conductance of the pure liquid is low (1×10^{-8} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$), the degree of ionisation of the pure liquid under ordinary conditions and the concentration of the proposed ions are expected to be very low.

Compounds of nitromethane with the Lewis acids, such as AlCl_3 , AlBr_3 , and the halides of Ti(IV) are known and in the case of FeCl_3 and AlCl_3 , the conductance of the solutions has also been studied^{1-5,7,10}. No effort has been made, however, to study the nature of the compounds formed. In the present work, it has been found that the Lewis acids, viz., SbCl_5 , TiCl_4 , SnCl_4 , and AsCl_3 , react with nitromethane exothermally. SbCl_5 and TiCl_4 form sparingly soluble compounds $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ and $\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$, whereas SnCl_4 and AsCl_3 are miscible with nitromethane in all proportions.

A measurement of specific conductance (Fig. 1) in the latter two cases indicates that

FIG. 1. Sp. conduc. of various Lewis acids in nitromethane at 30°.

33. Walden, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 385.

34. Spandau and Henning, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1958, 295, 281.

the solutions are quite conducting. Nitromethane has a low conductance (1×10^{-8} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ at 25°); AsCl_3 ³³ and SnCl_4 ³⁴ have also a very low conductance (12×10^{-7} and 6.3×10^{-11} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ at 25°) respectively. A much higher conductance of their mixtures with nitromethane clearly indicates that these react with it to produce compounds of more ionic in nature than the pure components. The breaks in these curves represent a change in ionic species and also the compositions of the compounds formed. The solid compound of SbCl_5 with nitromethane melts at 56°. The molten compound has a specific conductance of 3.384×10^{-3} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$. This again indicates the highly polar nature of the compound. In view of the low con-

ductance of SbCl_5^{35} and of the solvent, the formation of a compound, which is more ionic in nature than either of the components is indicated. The structures of these compounds can be safely represented as (II) as oxygen is a much stronger electron-donor than nitrogen; nitrogen in this particular case is already electron-deficient as it carries a partial positive charge.

TABLE II

Formation of solvates in nitromethane.

Compound.	Solvate.	M.P.	Ref. No.	Compound.	Solvate.	M.P.
AlCl_3	$\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{N}$	75-81°	8	SbCl_5	$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{N}$	63°
AlBr_3	$\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot \text{N}$	105-107°	9	..	$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{N}$	..
	(in benzene)		10	FeCl_3	$\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{N}$	> 220°
	$\text{AlBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{N}$		10	CaCl_2	$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	> 250°
	(in ethyl bromide)		10	MnCl_2	$\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	..
TiF_4	$\text{TiF}_4 \cdot \text{N}$	(not definite)		CdCl_2	$2\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	..
TiCl_4	$\text{TiCl}_4 \cdot \text{N}$	..		CuCl_2	$2\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	..
TiBr_4	$\text{TiBr}_4 \cdot \text{N}$	57-59°		ZnCl_2	$2\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	..
SbCl_5	$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{N}$	55°		HgCl_2	$2\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	..
AsCl_3	$\text{AsCl}_3 \cdot \text{N}$	..		NiCl_2	$2\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot \text{N}$	..
SnCl_4	$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{N}$	..				
	$\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{N}$	..				

N. B. N denotes nitromethane.

In Table II a list of the solvates formed between various compounds and nitromethane is presented. Aluminium³⁶ and arsenic halides^{37,38} are known to have a tendency to acquire tetra-co-ordination and SbCl_5^{39} , hexa-co-ordination and are therefore expected to act as monobasic acids. The structures of these compounds may be represented by (II). Hexa-co-ordination is the most stable co-ordination state for titanium³⁹ and tin³⁹ and therefore 1:2 compounds can be represented as (III).

35. Walden, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, **25**, 209.

36. Gröding, *Reo. trav. Chim.*, 1956, **75**, 8993.

37. Petzold, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, **214**, 355.

38. Dehn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 275.

39. Redlich *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **2**, 619.

1:1 Compound with SnCl_4 may be represented as in structure (IV) where hexa-coordination of tin is retained.

These structures cannot, however, account for the conductance of the solution. On the basis of the enolisation of nitromethane (V), the compound formed may be represented as (VI).

It is possible that the enolic hydrogen may ionise to provide conducting solutions due to the strong electron-attracting effect of the Lewis acids in these complexes:

In Fig. 2, molar conductances of the solutions of SbCl_5 , SnCl_4 , TiCl_4 , and AsCl_3 are plotted against the square root of the concentration. From the figure the order of the strengths of these acids at the concentration range studied appears to be: $\text{SbCl}_5 > \text{SnCl}_4 > \text{TiCl}_4 > \text{AsCl}_3$. This order is the same as has been observed in the solvents benzoyl chloride⁴⁰, acetyl chloride⁴¹, and dimethylformamide⁴². The molar conductance at infinite dilution has been found by extrapolating the curve and found to be 63, 33, 22 for SbCl_5 , SnCl_4 , and AsCl_3 respectively. In case of TiCl_4 , λ_0 has not been obtained as there seems a probability that the trend of the curve may have a sharp change beyond the concentration range studied.

FIG. 2. Plots of λc vs $\sqrt{c}$ of Lewis acids in nitromethane.

40. Singh *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 450.

41. Paul *et al.*, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 219, 222.

42. Paul *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1964, **2**, 87.

Protonic acids, like fluorosulphuric acid, sulphuric acid, acetic acid, formic acid are

miscible with nitromethane in all proportions. In Fig. 3 and 4, specific conductance of solutions of protonic acids has been plotted as a function of concentration as represented by molar ratio of acid/nitromethane.

FIG. 3. Specific conductance of protonic acids in nitromethane.

The solutions of protonic acids in CH_3NO_2 show higher conductance as compared to that of the pure solvent. This suggests that the solvent molecule may accept a proton from strong protonic acids. The conductance may be explained on the basis of the equilibria:

FIG. 4 Specific conductance of protonic acids in nitromethane at 30°.

At molar ratio, fluorosulphuric acid, solvent of 1:1, the conductance is 2.63×10^{-2} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 30° as compared to that of pure acid, 2.2×10^{-4} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°⁴³

Conductometric studies indicate the formation of the following compounds (Table III).

TABLE III

Compound.	Pure acid.	Specific conductance of	Solvent.	Compound.
$\text{HSO}_3\text{F} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$	2.2×10^{-4}	(43)	1×10^{-3}	2.63×10^{-2}
$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$	1.0×10^{-2}	(44)	"	8.75×10^{-3}
$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$	1.0×10^{-2}	"	"	2.00×10^{-3}
$\text{HCOOH} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$	64.0×10^{-6}	(45)	"	19.60×10^{-5}
$\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$	8.0×10^{-9}	(46)	"	6.70×10^{-6}

N.B. Figures in parentheses denote reference number.

Since the mechanism of the formation and conducting solutions seem to be quite different in the case of protonic acids as compared to the Lewis acids, it will not be without interest to construct a plot of equivalent conductance vs. square root of the concentration. Such a plot is presented in Fig. 5. The general values of equivalent conductance are low as compared to that of the Lewis acids and this is not unexpected in view of the protonic nature of the solvent itself, being slightly acidic.

FIG. 5. Plots of λc vs $\sqrt{c}$ of protonic acids in nitromethane at 30° .

The equivalent conductance at infinite dilution has been obtained by extrapolating the curve and is found to be 26 and 18 in the case of fluorosulphuric acid and sulphuric acid respectively. The proton mobility is very low as compared to other protonic solvents (HCl in $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} = 198.5^{47}$, HCl in $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 426.17^{48}$). This indicates that the solvent does not accept the proton easily.

43. Greenwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 415.

44. Bergins, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 72, 338.

45. Schlesingen and Coleman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 271.

46. Hopfgartner, *Compt. rend.*, 1853, 34, 1313.

47. Shedlovsky and Kay *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 151.

48. Longworth, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2741.

Another proof of this is furnished by the conductance of acetic acid in this solvent. The conductance falls till 1:1 molar ratio of acid/solvent is obtained, because both the compounds are poor proton-donors. The values of conductance obtained for molar ratio of protonic acid/nitromethane 1:1 clearly indicate the following order of proton-donating strength: $\text{HSO}_3\text{F} > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{HCOOH} > \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$.

Organic tertiary bases are miscible with nitromethane in all proportions. Since heat is neither evolved nor absorbed in this process, one can safely say that there is no apparent reaction. Conductances of systems pyridine-nitromethane, piperidine-nitromethane, triethylamine-nitromethane have already been studied⁷. The solutions of these organic tertiary bases do not have a high conductance in this solvent. Plots of $\sqrt{c}$ vs. λc have been drawn for various bases, viz., α -picoline, dimethylaniline, and quinoline, in Fig. 6. The same plots have also been made for benzylamine, piperidine, triethylamine, and *n*-butylamine and are shown in Fig. 7. The first category of bases are weak and have the following order: quinoline $>$ α -picoline $>$ pyridine $>$ dimethylaniline, whereas for the second set, the order of the basicity is piperidine $>$ triethylamine $>$ *n*-butylamine $>$ benzylamine.

FIG. 6. Plots of λc vs. $\sqrt{c}$ of bases in nitromethane at 30°.

The conductance may be explained as due to the formation of the following ion pairs:

Plots of $\log c$ vs. $\log \lambda c$ are presented in Fig. 8 A and 8 B.

For an electrolyte, which undergoes ionisation to furnish only two ions as suggested above, the theoretical curve of $\log c$ vs. $\log \lambda c$ should be linear with slope equal to $-1/2$ provided that the degree of ionisation is very small as compared to unity. It is rather difficult to account for slope of $-3/4$ which requires that ionisation reaction produces four ions per mole of the solvent. Hence there is a possibility that these bases providing a slope of $-3/4$ exist as dimers:

FIG. 8B. Plots of $\log c$ vs. $\log \lambda c$ for bases.

and if α is the fraction of ionised dimer at a molar concentration c of the dimer, it follows that the overall ionisation constant K_b of the base will be given by

$$K_b = \frac{(2\alpha c)^2 (2\alpha c)^2}{(1-\alpha)c}$$

α is given by the conductance ratio $\lambda c/\lambda_0$ and if it is very small compared to unity for the concentration range studied, it follows that

$$\frac{d \log \lambda c}{d \log c} = -3/4$$

where $d \log c$ is the small change in $\log c$ and $d \log \lambda c$ is the corresponding small change in $\log \lambda c$.

The plots of $\log \lambda c$ vs. $\log c$ for the four bases *n*-butylamine, piperidine, benzylamine, and triethylamine are shown in Fig. 8A. The slope has been found to be -0.75 in all these cases and it indicates that these exist as dimers in nitromethane. The mechanism by which dimerisation occurs may be analogous to the one proposed for bases in dimethylformamide⁴⁹ and acetonitrile⁵⁰.

It may be in other forms like

In contrast to these, similar plots for the other set of organic tertiary bases like α -picoline, quinoline, and pyridine provide slope of $-1/2$ which indicates that these bases do not dimerise and give rise to two ions on dissociation:

Thus it may be concluded from this work that nitromethane is a protonic solvent and its autoionisation may be represented as:

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitromethane (Eastman Kodak) was kept over anhydrous calcium chloride (A.R.) overnight, decanted, and distilled through a long column. Middle fraction (about 50%) was taken and was again fractionally distilled through a long fractionating column and the distillate collected at take-off ratio of 5:1 (b.p. 101°/760 mm) having specific conductance $1.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 30°. Other solvents like carbon tetrachloride, benzene, etc. were purified and dried carefully before use by usual methods.

Lewis acids like $TiCl_4$, $SbCl_5$, $SbCl_3$, $AsCl_3$ of pure grade were further purified by distillation as reported earlier⁵¹, whereas $SnCl_4$ was prepared from A.R. tin and subsequently purified.

49. Paul *et al.*, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 335.

50. Muney and Wetzee, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 89.

51. Paul *et al.*, unpublished.

Protonic acids like sulphuric acid, acetic acid, formic acid were made anhydrous according to methods suggested earlier⁵²⁻⁵⁴. Fluorosulphuric acid was prepared from fuming sulphuric acid by addition of potassium bifluoride, as already reported⁵³.

Organic tertiary bases were kept over solid potassium hydroxide overnight and were distilled before use. Quinoline, however, was purified by complex formation with zinc chloride under similar conditions, as described earlier⁵⁵.

Metal chlorides used were dehydrated by passing dry HCl gas over heated chloride for about 2 hours. These were then placed in a vacuum desiccator over P_2O_5 to remove any excess of HCl. Anhydrous iron(III) chloride was prepared by reacting ordinary $FeCl_3$ with thionyl chloride and finally subliming⁵⁶.

Conductance Measurement.—Resistance of different solutions was measured by using a precision measuring bridge, type WBR No. 108, with logarithmic indicator amplifier, type TAV, IKC No. 034 (Wissenschaftlich Technische Werkstätten Weilheim/Oby, Germany), as reported earlier⁵⁷. A cell of cell constant 2.54 cm^{-1} was employed for solutions having high conductance, but for measuring low conductances, a cell having a cell constant of 0.0748 was employed.

Solvates.—Antimony(v) chloride (15 g.) on addition to excess of well-cooled nitromethane (25 ml) and subsequent treatment (washing with dry carbon tetrachloride and drying in low vacuum) afforded a yellowish white crystalline salt (m.p. 55°); specific conductance of molten solvate at 55° is $3.384 \times 10^{-3} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This is hygroscopic in nature. (Found: Sb, 33.63; Cl, 48.97. $SbCl_5 \cdot CH_3NO_2$ requires Sb, 33.80; Cl, 49.28%).

Antimony(III) chloride (10 g.) on addition to nitromethane (25 ml) dissolved and on cooling a colorless crystalline salt separated. The solid (Ia) was filtered washed with CCl_4 and dried in vacuum to furnish $SbCl_3 \cdot CH_3NO_2$, m.p. 63° . (Found: Sb, 41.73; Cl, 36.52. $SbCl_3 \cdot CH_3NO_2$ requires Sb, 42.07; Cl, 36.72%).

On addition of dry benzene to the solution after separating (Ia), a white sticky compound separated. It was washed with dry CCl_4 and dried. Melting point could not be determined due to its sticky nature. (Found: Sb, 34.62; Cl, 29.93. $SbCl_3 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2$ requires Sb, 34.81; Cl, 30.38%).

Anhydrous iron(III) chloride (15 g.) was added to nitromethane (30 ml) and warmed. On cooling and addition of light petroleum, a dark brown powder separated. (Found: Fe, 19.51; Cl, 37.12. $FeCl_3 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2$ requires Fe, 19.69; Cl, 37.43%).

Anhydrous chlorides of calcium, cadmium, copper, zinc, mercury, and nickel (10 g. each) were added to nitromethane (25 ml) and refluxed for 48 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered through a sintered glass funnel in a dry atmosphere and the residue washed with an inert solvent. The results of analysis and the compositions of the solvates formed are recorded in Table III. Cobalt chloride does not form any solvate with nitromethane.

52. Paul and Malhotra, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1963, **321**, 70.

53. Paul *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 820.

54. Garner *et al.*, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, **46**, 236.

55. Paul *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind., Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 533.

56. Hecht, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1947, **254**, 37.

57. Paul *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, **321**, 56.

TABLE III

Solute.	Solvate.	% Metal.		% Chloride.	
		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
CaCl ₂	CaCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	23.02	23.25	40.91	41.28
MnCl ₂	MnCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	29.20	29.41	37.63	37.97
CdCl ₂	2CdCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	52.21	52.57	32.82	33.17
CuCl ₂	2CuCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	38.17	38.48	42.83	43.03
ZnCl ₂	2ZnCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	38.86	39.04	42.41	42.64
HgCl ₂	2HgCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	66.31	66.42	23.32	23.51
NiCl ₂	2NiCl ₂ .CH ₃ NO ₂	36.52	36.76	44.01	44.23

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Received November 13, 1964.